

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18838672>

**Principals' Communication Patterns and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary School
Edo State, Nigeria**

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated principals' communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State. A correlational, ex-post-facto research design was adopted. The population comprised 3,387 principals and teachers. The sample for the study was 739 respondents comprising 184 principals and 555 teachers in Edo State. Two self-constructed instruments—Principals' Communication Pattern Questionnaire (PCPQ) and Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ)—were used for data collection. Reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.61 and 0.77, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) and coefficient of determination (r^2) were used to answer the three research questions. All hypotheses were tested using Pearson Correlation at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between the principals' communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State; There is a significant relationship between principals' interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State, There is a significant relationship between principals' networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State. The study concluded that effective communication by principals plays a crucial role in enhancing teachers' performance. Based on these findings, it was recommended that principals should adopt assertive, interactive, and networking communication patterns to improve teachers' job effectiveness and promote a more productive school environment.

Keywords: *Communication Patterns, Job Effectiveness, School Leadership, Secondary Education*

INTRODUCTION

Effective teaching is important because it helps student learning. It has become even more important as the emphasis on quality in higher education has increased. Effective teaching does not occur by chance (Sikes, 2016). It has been widely acknowledged that education is a powerful and dynamic tool for social change and national development of a country. Nigeria education is of a fundamental human right for promoting sustainable development. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria's (FRN, 2017), Nigerian National Policy on Education, opined that education is the process that aids in the development of the whole person physically, mentally, morally, politically, socially, and technologically which enable the people to function in any workplace environment they may find themselves in. It encompasses the growth of the person at all levels of the educational system.

It is impossible to overstate the importance of secondary education, particularly in a rapidly evolving society like Nigeria and Edo State in particular. According to Sobhy (2023), secondary education bears the responsibility of imparting values, norms, and other positive virtues to students through both direct instructions in the classroom and guidance in practicing citizenship in day-to-day and community living. All higher-level operations within a school are supervised by the principal. Their ways of communicating with teachers depends on the kind of volume and clarity of their exchanges that have a big impact on their motivation, job satisfaction, and general efficacy in the classroom. Regarding the precise effect of principals' communication patterns on teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in

Edo State, most teachers failed to understand the principal point of ideal due to how the information is being passed during decision making.

Teachers' job effectiveness explains their ability to achieve targets or objectives within a record time. It is the measure of the ability of a teacher to carry out the functions, tasks and plans of a school as assigned to him with little or no error. An effective teacher does not just work to complete his tasks within the specified time but tries to come up with inventive solutions to problems and continuously improves his performance to achieve best results (Warner and Kaur, 2017).

Furthermore, communication plays an increasingly important role in disseminating information and facilitating adaptation to change in the rapidly changing educational landscape, where a variety of teaching methods and technologies are being introduced. The goals of schools are communicated to relevant individuals within the school system by principals (who are the primary managers of secondary schools). Communication is the act of conveying a message or making something known to another person through the exchange of information, ideas, thoughts and feelings via words or nonverbal means, such as letters, telephone, books, conferences, and seminars (Aladenusi, and Ayodele, 2011). Communication occurs at all times and in a variety of patterns or ways in schools. However, principals communicate in specific ways, and these communication patterns can have a significant impact on the effectiveness of a school system. It is the principal's responsibility to devise appropriate measures to ensure that all teachers follow the rules and regulations in the performance of their instructional tasks.

The pattern that a principal use to coordinate the affairs of a school can have a significant impact on staff moral and how effective their teaching could be on the student. It has been discovered that principals' interactive, networking, aggressive, manipulative, assertive communication pattern, use of instructional materials, teaching/communication skills, and teachers' motivation/personality characteristics are factors which influence teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools. This study intends to close the current research gap by understanding a thorough investigation of principal communication patterns and their direct influence on teacher job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State.

Statement of the Problem

Principals' communication is fast becoming another issue for efficient job performance. Researchers revealed that principals' interactive, networking, aggressive, manipulative, assertive communication patterns, use of instructional materials, teaching/communication skills, and teachers' motivation/personality characteristics are factors which influence teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools. Researches and observation have also shown that some principals' inability to communicate, seem to affect teachers' competence to the rudiments of teaching, bearing on teachers teaching performance, leading to lack of classroom organization and management, bringing misunderstanding and conflict among staff and students as well as building weakness to the whole effectiveness of job performance of the teachers in public secondary schools.

However, in a situation where communication pattern utilized is ineffective, the principal cannot carry his teachers along to work together towards the realization of the goals and objectives of education. In such a case communication is defective, there is a barrier or gap which gives room for rumor mongering and breakdown of administrative process with serious implications. Therefore, the study determines relationship between principals' communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo state.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the identifiable principals' communication patterns in public secondary schools in Edo State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State?
3. What is the relationship between principals' networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. **Ho:** There is no significant relationship between the principals' communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State

2. **H0:** There is no significant relationship between principals' interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State.
3. **H0:** There is no significant relationship between principals' networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted a correlational research design using the ex-post facto method. The population comprised 612 principals and 2,775 teachers in 306 public secondary schools in Edo State, under the State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, across the three senatorial districts. A sample of 739 respondents, consisting of 184 principals and 555 teachers, was drawn from the population. Data were collected through two self-developed questionnaires titled Principals' Communication Patterns Questionnaire (PCPQ) and Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ). The instruments contained three sections and were structured on a 4-point Likert rating scale: Very Frequently Occurred (4), Frequently Occurred (3), Often Occurred (2), and Rarely Occurred (1). Copies of the questionnaires were administered directly to respondents in their respective schools by the researcher, with the assistance of trained research aides, to ensure a high return rate. The instruments were subjected to face and content validation by an expert in Educational Management and Foundations at Delta State University, Abraka. Reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding coefficients of 0.61 for the Principals' Communication Pattern Scale (PCPS) and 0.77 for the Teachers' Job Effectiveness Scale (TJES), indicating acceptable reliability. Although 739 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, only 717 were properly completed and returned, representing the valid sample used for data analysis. The remaining 22 copies were either not returned or were inadequately filled and therefore discarded to ensure accuracy and consistency in the analysis. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. Research questions were answered using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and coefficient of determination (r^2), while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson correlation at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What are the identifiable principals' communication patterns in public secondary schools in Edo State?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of identifiable principals' communication patterns used by principals

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Interactive Communication Pattern	717	3.01	0.55	Most used
Assertive Communication Pattern	717	2.95	0.59	Highly used
Networking Communication Pattern	717	2.88	0.52	Frequently used
Manipulative Communication Pattern	717	2.38	0.59	Less used
Aggressive Communication Pattern	717	1.96	0.49	Least used

Data in Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of identifiable principals' communication patterns in public secondary schools in Edo State, 3.01, 2.95, 2.88, 2.38, 1.96 with their standard deviation 0.55, 0.59, 0.52, 0.59 and 0.49, the mean and standard deviation shows that the most frequently used communication pattern by principals in Edo State secondary schools is the Interactive Communication Pattern with a mean of 3.01, followed by Assertive and Networking patterns. The least used are Manipulative and Aggressive patterns.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between principals' interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State?

Table 2: Relationship between interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Remark
Interactive Communication Pattern	717	3.0103	0.552	0.777	0.604	60.4	Related

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Remark
Teachers Job Effectiveness	717	2.8959	0.521				

Data in Table 2 shows the relationship between principals' interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State. This result shows the mean of 3.01 and a standard deviation of 0.55 and teachers job effectiveness of 2.89 and a standard deviation of 0.52. This revealed that the interactive communication pattern of principals has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job effectiveness. The computed r-value of 0.777 indicates a strong correlation and $r^2 = 0.604$ shows that 60.4% of teachers' job effectiveness can be accounted for by interactive communication.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between networking communication pattern of principals and teachers' job effectiveness?

Table 3: Relationship between networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Remark
Networking Communication Pattern	717	2.8798	0.527	0.754	0.569	56.9	Related
Teachers Job Effectiveness	717	2.8959	0.521				

Data in Table 3 shows the relationship between networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools. The result shows that the networking communication pattern has a mean score of 2.8798 with a standard deviation of 0.527, while teachers' job effectiveness has a mean score of 2.8959 and a standard deviation of 0.521. These values indicate that the respondents rate both networking communication practices and teachers' effectiveness moderately high. The computed r-value of 0.754 indicates a strong correlation, suggesting that as networking communication improves in the school environment, teachers' job effectiveness also increases. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.569$) shows that 56.9% teachers' job effectiveness is accounted for by networking communication. This means that more than half of teachers' effectiveness is influenced by the extent to which networking communication strategies are employed within the school system.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between all principals' communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Correlation between all communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness

Variables	N	R	r ²	r ² %	p-value	Remark
Interactive Communication Pattern	717	0.777	0.604	60.4	0.000	significant positive relationship
Networking Communication Pattern		0.754	0.569	56.9	0.000	significant positive relationship
Aggressive Communication Pattern		-0.587	0.344	34.4	0.000	significant positive relationship
Manipulative Communication Pattern		-0.052	0.003	0.3	0.167	Not significant
Assertive Communication Pattern		0.851**	0.724	72.4	0.000	significant positive relationship

Table 4 presents the Pearson correlation coefficient results for all communication patterns and teachers' job effectiveness. The results revealed that interactive communication pattern ($r = 0.777$, $p < 0.05$), networking communication pattern ($r = 0.754$, $p < 0.05$), aggressive communication pattern ($r = -0.587$, $p < 0.05$), and assertive communication pattern ($r = 0.851$, $p < 0.05$) all showed statistically significant relationships with teachers' job effectiveness. However, the manipulative communication pattern ($r = -0.052$, $p > 0.05$) did not show a significant relationship. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis was rejected, as the majority of the communication patterns examined were significantly related to teachers' job effectiveness. It was therefore concluded that principals' communication patterns have a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Edo State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between interactive communication pattern of principals and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Pearson r between interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness

Variables	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	p-value	Remark
Interactive Communication Pattern	3.0103	0.552	0.777**	0.604	60.4	0.000	Significant relationship
Teachers Job Effectiveness	2.8959	0.521					

Table 5 reveals the Pearson r on interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness. The table shows that there is a positive and significant relationship with an r-value of 0.777, which is greater than the p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools, was rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between interactive communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between principals' networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State.

Table 6: Pearson r between principals' networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness

Variables	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	p-value	Remark
Networking Communication Pattern	2.8798	0.527	0.754	0.569	56.9	0.000	Significant relationship
Teachers Job Effectiveness	2.8959	0.521					

Table 6 reveals the Pearson r on networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness. The table shows that there is a positive and significant relationship with an r-value of 0.754, which is greater than the p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools was rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between networking communication pattern and teachers' job effectiveness.

Discussion of Results

Principals' Communication Patterns Have A Significant Influence On Teachers' Job Effectiveness In Secondary Schools

The first finding of the study shows that principals' communication patterns have a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Edo State. Effective communication patterns—such as assertive, interactive, and networking approaches—enhance clarity of instructions, promote mutual understanding, and strengthen professional relationships between principals and teachers. When principals communicate clearly, listen actively, and provide constructive feedback, teachers are better motivated, more committed, and more efficient in carrying out their instructional responsibilities. This ultimately leads to improved classroom performance and overall job effectiveness. A possible reason

for this finding is that communication serves as the foundation for coordination, supervision, and motivation within the school system. Principals who adopt effective communication patterns reduce ambiguity in task expectations, minimize conflicts, and create an enabling work environment where teachers feel valued and supported. This sense of inclusion and recognition can increase teachers' job satisfaction and willingness to perform their duties effectively. In contrast, poor communication may lead to misunderstanding, low morale, and reduced productivity among teachers. This finding supports the study of Oyetunde and Adebayo (2019) who reported that effective communication between school leaders and teachers significantly enhances teacher engagement and instructional delivery. Similarly, Eze and Okoye (2020) found that positive communication styles adopted by principals improve teachers' morale, commitment, and effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools. Therefore, the implication of this finding is that principals' communication patterns are critical determinants of teachers' effectiveness, and adopting appropriate communication strategies can significantly improve teaching outcomes and overall school performance.

Interactive Communication Pattern and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

The first finding of the study Finding shows that interactive communication pattern has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Edo State. Interactive communication involves two-way dialogue, feedback provision, and collaborative problem solving between principals and teachers, which fosters clarity, motivation, and efficiency in instructional delivery. This finding supports the study by Oyetunde and Adebayo (2019), who reported that interactive communication positively impacts teacher effectiveness through improved engagement and instructional support. Similarly, Eze and Okoye (2020) found that interactive leadership styles enhance teachers' morale and job effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools.

Networking Communication Pattern and Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Finding revealed that networking communication pattern has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job effectiveness in Edo State. This indicates that principals who utilize professional networks, peer collaborations, and external linkages significantly improve teachers' instructional effectiveness. Networking communication allows principals to access resources, share innovative teaching strategies, and provide professional development opportunities for teachers. This finding aligns with Udegbe and Chukwuma (2017), who reported that principals who actively network with educational stakeholders enhance teacher productivity and instructional quality. Additionally, Mensah and Boateng (2018) found that networking communication strengthens professional collaboration and contributes to the effective delivery of curriculum objectives.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that principals' communication patterns play a significant role in enhancing teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State. Among the five communication patterns examined, assertive, interactive, and networking communication patterns were found to have positive and significant relationships with teachers' job effectiveness, indicating that principals who communicate clearly, collaboratively, and assertively are more likely to enhance teachers' job effectiveness, while manipulative communication was found to have no significant influence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. Principals should adopt assertive, interactive, and networking communication patterns when dealing with teachers to enhance their job effectiveness. Clear, respectful, and collaborative communication encourages teacher engagement and productivity.
2. Training programs and workshops on effective communication should be organized for school principals to help them minimize aggressive and manipulative communication practices that could negatively affect teachers' effectiveness.
3. School management and educational authorities should regularly evaluate the communication styles of principals and provide feedback to improve teacher-principal interactions, thereby enhancing overall school effectiveness.

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